

APPLYING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS FOR DEVELOPING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING

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***Abstract.** This article discusses how to use authentic materials to improve intercultural communication skills. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the cultural aspect of foreign language training, and teachers are increasingly expected to help their students to achieve intercultural competency. Furthermore, using actual resources into teaching culture is a powerful motivator, as it allows students to recognize that there is a community of users who speak the other languages.*

***Keywords:** self-consciousness, integration, socio-cultural milieu, consciousness, cognitive demands, legitimacy, interlocutor, phenomenon, prospective, prejudices.*

In today's society, a graduate of a linguistic university is held to very high standards. It must be an expert in intercultural communication in addition to having a good command of a foreign language. It is clear that language and culture are inextricably linked. "Language is a mirror of culture, it reflects not only the real world that surrounds a person, not only the real conditions of his life, but also the public self-consciousness of the people, his mentality, national character, lifestyle, traditions, customs, morality, system values, attitude, and world vision." [Ter-Minasova S, 2000]

One of the most pressing issues in foreign language instruction today is the need for a more in-depth understanding of the world of native speakers. In recent decades, the European paradigm of teaching foreign languages has emphasized intercultural competency as a learning goal. Language is intended to be considered both an object of study and a means of learning, according to existing theories. The study of a foreign language does not mean the separation of linguistic characteristics and types of speech activity, but rather their integration - learning everything at the same time while immersed in the cultural context [Kramsch C, 1993].

In domestic linguodidactics studies, similar approaches to setting goals and changing the content of teaching a foreign language are also offered. Every step of

the way, foreign language teachers are confronted with the socio-cultural milieu and linguo-culturological issues. "Each foreign language lesson is a crossroads of cultures, a practice of intercultural dialogue, because every foreign word reflects a foreign world and a foreign culture: behind each word is a national consciousness (again, foreign) idea of the world".

A student of foreign languages need certain basic information in order to communicate effectively with native speakers. It's hard to master a language as a medium of communication without first comprehending the mindsets of the people you'll be interacting with. It is vital to have a basic understanding of the history, state, social and economic structure, and customs and traditions of the country where the language is being studied. As a result, in order to equip students with the essential background information, language study and instruction should be handled in such a way that they become acquainted with the culture of the nation in which the language is studied at the same time. Background knowledge and the capacity to apply it effectively will be indicators of the development of intercultural communication competence. Only a few of the skills and talents that make up intercultural competence are included here. These include:

- a positive attitude toward another culture and its bearers;
- the ability to correctly interpret a partner's language behavior;
- the ability to initiate and maintain intercultural dialogue;
- the ability to see similarities and differences between communicating cultures and apply them in the context of intercultural communication;
- the ability to put oneself in the shoes of an interlocutor
- a representative of another culture;
- the ability to put oneself in the shoes of a partner;
- the ability to put oneself in the shoes of an interlocutor
- a representative of another culture;
- the ability to avoid or resolve intercultural conflicts and contradictions, rejection of prejudices and stereotypes;
- the ability to operate with various verbal and nonverbal means to achieve mutual understanding between cultures;
- the ability to consciously vary the choice of speech operations depending on the goals and situation of communication.

Intercultural competence, on the other hand, is only one component of a larger set of skills that a person learning a foreign language employs in communicative activity. Competencies are traditionally separated into two categories: general and communicative. Without a doubt, the primary goal of a teacher in a practical foreign

language course is to help pupils develop their own language skills. However, the training must include the linguistic and cultural aspects of the instruction. One of the requirements is that the textbook use modern language material. The textbook's topic should be relevant to current issues in society.

It has been traditionally supposed that the language presented to learners should be simplified in some way for easy access and acquisition. Nowadays there are recommendations that the language presented should be authentic” [Widdowson H,1990]. Students' curiosity is piqued by appeals to modernity, which leads to an increase in another educational component required for motivation is the truthfulness of textbooks. Authentic texts have the advantage of representing actual language material, illustrating how the language functions in the form used by native speakers and in a natural social setting. As a result, authentic texts are the finest way to teach the culture of the target language's country. Because it is not always possible to utilize actual texts in guides for beginners learning a foreign language, specifically prepared or adapted texts prevail at the beginning of the learning process. However, it is advisable to use the original language material in textbooks for university students who continue to study a foreign language beyond high school. The English-language press could be a source of such information. It's worth noting that newspaper and magazine articles offer a wealth of chances for analyzing contemporary sociocultural data. Students' cognitive demands should be met by texts that engage their cognitive curiosity, provide new knowledge on an existing problem, and provide creative ideas and non-traditional techniques to covering the topic.

The authenticity of the texts' structure and content, as well as their stylistic diversity, boosts students' enthusiasm and offers the best circumstances for effective immersion in the linguistic environment during English practical sessions. The study of such works allows one to delve into a foreign country culture and grasp native speakers' ordinary lexicon. Authentic texts provide the most communicative and meaningful vocabulary units to a foreign language learner. At the same time, the assimilation of terms with the advanced national-cultural component is taking place. Teaching a foreign language necessitates the development of not just linguistic, but also sociolinguistic and pragmatic skills. This includes things like politeness standards, proverbs, and popular idioms, as well as the ability to expand and generalize information gleaned from a variety of written and audio texts. In oral communication, the ability to extract the essential information is established, as is the ability to apply it in varied forms, volumes, and situations. Students must be able to master the principles for creating statements and utilize them to execute a variety of

communicative duties, including expressing their own opinions, persuading, debating, proving, and explaining. The following are some examples of tasks:

1. Demonstrate or reject the legitimacy of the article's author's opinion;
2. Express your own thoughts on the topic;
3. Examine the facts in the text and draw your own conclusions;
4. Define this phenomenon in your own words.

As recent research in the field of foreign language teaching methods have revealed, studying a foreign language and developing a foreign culture is impossible without referring to one's own language and culture. It is necessary to compare and contrast cultural and national values and customs. It is insufficient for a teacher to confine himself to correcting grammatical and phonetic problems in order to build students' communication abilities. You should also attract students' attention to the national characteristics of English-speaking cultures, and encourage them to comprehend why people who speak a different language speak, act, and react the way they do. Students must know and respect the interlocutor's cultural traditions in order to speak effectively and create mutual understanding, without compromising their own identity.

To summarize, authentic materials, without a doubt, are a rich supply of cultural material. Teachers should not be scared to use authentic materials because they are a lot of fun to work with, as well as motivating and instructional. Authentic materials must be carefully picked and prepared, but they are well worth the effort. Finally, in the relaxed atmosphere of the language classroom, learners should openly debate and compare the selected cultural elements to their own culture. Learners who are exposed to authentic materials on a regular basis may get more familiar with them and may be able to avoid cultural shock while visiting the culture in issue in the future. It is necessary to draw students' attention to the differences and similarities of culture in all types of work, while emphasizing that neither our culture nor the culture of English speakers is "better" or "worse," but rather distinct, and we must take this into account in order to communicate effectively and achieve mutual understanding. As a result, foreign language teachers must comprehend what is behind the new skills and methods that their students must learn in order to achieve intercultural comprehension. Language teachers will be better equipped to integrate cultural practices into their instruction if they become more aware and skilled about the subject.

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